

EIC COMMUNITIES

D2.2 CoPs Animation - first version

WP2: Community and synergy building between EIC portfolios and projects.

Task 2.2. Co-creation of CoPs community and synergy building activities

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Technical references

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Introduction

The EIC Communities Project

The “EIC Communities” objective is to increase both the visibility and impact of the European Innovation Council (EIC)-funded projects by stimulating synergies and innovation breakthroughs. It aims to select, involve, and actively engage key organisations who have a vested interest in their activities and results, such as scientific innovators, policy makers, and industry leaders.

The project’s aim is to create three thematic Communities of Practice (CoPs) in the CleanTech, Industry and Health sectors by co-creating diverse online and physical activities, materials and tools that encourage multidisciplinary interactions among EIC deep-tech projects. Working closely with EIC representatives and EIC Programme Managers (PMs), the project will pioneer new engagement practices and offer policy recommendations for research and innovation in the future of deep tech.

The goal is to propel future technologies and innovations, driving towards a more connected and innovative future for broad, diverse and gender-inclusive deep tech communities.

This document finds its basis on deliverable 2.1 “CoP: Governance structure and management that meant to constitute a framework for the governance and management of Communities of Practices. Subsequent releases, featuring updates on the governance and structure, will be an ongoing process. This document is the first update of that deliverable and include the experience gained with the implementation of the initial activities with the EIC beneficiaries and stakeholders that participate to the Communities of Practice. Other updates are foreseen M20 (April 2025) and M30 (February 2026) in order to update the governance structure according to the assessed needs.

Background & Context

The community built around the European Innovation Council has united and is curating a wide range of deep tech projects and entrepreneurs with more than 5,500 quality-stamped companies, 408 innovation-driven research teams and 800 innovations, and more than 2,800 corporates, investors, procures and many more business intermediaries and market experts (EIC Pilot Impact Report 2021).

Building communities around EIC themes and challenges, encouraging interactions among them, is crucial for the EIC ecosystem. These collaborative efforts involve high levels of teamwork and pushing innovation across EIC projects. Creating inclusive communities and connections among EIC topics is vital for research and promoting collaborations across different fields. It helps EIC Project Managers oversee projects effectively and adapt to changes in the scientific and industrial world.

The main goal of EIC Communities project (or CSA project) is to make EIC projects more visible and impactful. This means working together on online and offline activities, resources,

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and tools in three Communities of Practice (CoP): CleanTech, Industry, and Health. These structures are designed to support diverse communities centred on specific themes, promoting teamwork within and across EIC challenges. CoPs also give EIC Project Managers a solid support and a good plan to build networks around these themes. In the end, these efforts will lead to new ideas about future technologies and important suggestions to keep deep-tech projects moving forward.

This report explains how to set up and run a CoP effectively. It involves careful planning, coordination and ongoing support. It is meant to be a living report to be refined over the duration of the project.

Purpose & Scope of a CoP

A CoP is a collective formed by individuals sharing common interests with the objective to learn, exchange knowledge, and refine their expertise within a specific field or domain. It aims to cultivate an environment that encourages sharing experiences, best practices, and insights among its members, thereby contributing to their collective growth and development.

In building a CoP, it is essential to define the common objectives, its scope and maintain focus. The scope of the CoP was defined in the CSA project proposal and further refined in the co-creation workshop, that took place in Brussels on 23rd October 2023 benefitting from the contribution of EIC Programme Managers (EIC PM) and project's partners. It sets the specific domains each CoP emphasizes on, maintaining focus and relevance while ensuring that the identified topics are broad enough to encourage meaningful knowledge exchange, while they are not too narrow so that they can limit the knowledge exchange and learning.

Moreover, bilateral meetings between CSA team and the EIC PMs grouped in CoP themes, held in M4, have helped the CSA team in this action of identifying the precise objective of each CoP and actions and activities to be managed to assure the sustainability of the CoPs. These bilateral meetings were meant to be a follow-up of the co-creation workshop held in Brussels, to strengthen the relations with the EIC PMs.

CoP members early in the co-creation process agree on their CoP objectives, they should maintain focus as it is crucial to avoid unrelated discussions while ensuring alignment with the CoP's objectives. This approach fosters purposeful exchanges and collaborations, leading to more impactful learning experiences. However, due to evolution of CoPs composition i.e. new funded projects, PMs that will leave and will be replaced, new objectives and scopes coming up and new trends or innovations, the CSA team is aware that some adaptability is needed during the CSA project lifetime, but always within the framework established in this document. This is done through constant evaluation and feedback mechanisms as they play a pivotal role in refining the co-creation process. This ongoing assessment seeks to enhance the CoP's effectiveness and ensure its continuous evolution to best serve its members.

Building the CoP

Methodology used to build the CoP:

The following methodology was used when building the CoPs and is explained further:

1. Surveying EIC PMs to select EIC-funded projects and identify needs and challenges for future networking and synergies.
2. Identifying crucial stakeholders with a vested interest in CoPs and subsequently assessing them.
3. Designing co-creation workshops and implementing them to build the CoP objective, activities and follow-up along with its members.

1/Surveying EIC PMs to select EIC-funded projects and identify needs and challenges for future networking and synergies.

The purpose of this task was to gather insights from EIC Programme Managers about which projects would benefit most from being part of a CoP and to identify specific needs and challenges that can be addressed through networking and collaborative efforts. EIC PMs were instructed to share lists of EIC projects that would benefit from the project. Those projects would have interest in networking opportunities and potential areas for synergy with other projects. Reminders were sent to ensure a high response rate and help if needed.

The outcomes were the identification of EIC-funded projects that would benefit most from a CoP, the clear understanding of the key challenges and needs that the CoP can address (completed during the co-creation workshop of October 2023) and a data-driven basis for planning CoP activities and objectives.

2/Identifying crucial stakeholders with a vested interest in CoPs and subsequently assessing them.

The purpose was to identify stakeholders who have a significant interest in the success and outcomes of the CoP and to assess their motivations, expectations, and potential contributions.

All partners were in charge of identifying and mobilizing those stakeholders. EBN conducted an info session on the 7th of February 2024 to present the project and identify the potential EBN members who could take part.

Project partners organised community building workshops/ co-creation sessions to which EIC beneficiaries and stakeholders were invited. They took place on the 21st of February for Industry CoP, 27th of February for CleanTech CoP and the 13th of March 2024 for Health CoP to discuss EIC beneficiaries and stakeholder's views on the CoP's potential activities and objectives. The workshops gathered EIC beneficiaries and stakeholders' needs and interests. The relevant categories of stakeholders were among other ways identified with the help of EIC PMs in the Brussels co-creation workshop of October 23, 2023. The results were described in Deliverable D1.1.

EBN CoP managers have tailored communication strategies to different stakeholders, targeting the Special Interest Group Members. Stakeholders are kept informed about CoP developments, upcoming events, and opportunities for involvement through the EBN newsletter and SIG newsletters. They are actively encouraged to participate in CoP activities, offering roles that align with their interests and expertise.

A comprehensive list of key stakeholders with detailed profiles of their interests and potential contributions was collected through the questionnaires that were disseminated since December 2023.

3/Designing co-creation workshops and implementing them in order to build the CoP objective, activities and follow-up along with its members.

As mentioned in point 2 the first step to concrete establish the CoP was the organization of community building workshops, that took place online according to the following dates:

- 21st February 2024: CoP Industry
- 27th February 2024: CoP CleanTech
- 13th March 2024: CoP Health

As for CoP a new EIC PM, Federica Zanca were going to be appointed and it was not possible to include her project in this phase, an additional event for her project's portfolio was organized online on 24th April 2024.

The purpose was to collaboratively develop the objectives, activities, and follow-up plans for the CoP with input from its members, ensuring the CoP is built on shared goals and active participation.

- Project partners designed the workshops objectives, setting the goals for the workshops, selecting the facilitators and planning interactive sessions using the online tools (Zoom, Miro).
- The sessions planned were interactive sessions, including brainstorming and group exercises to foster collaboration and idea generation.
- Participants were sent preparatory materials, including agendas, objectives, and background information.
- Facilitators were used in the break-out rooms to animate the sessions and ensuring that all participants participate and are engaged.
- Feedback forms were sent to collect feedback on the co-creation sessions and participants provided some positive feedback to the co-creation workshops.
- The outcomes of each workshop, including decisions made and action item were recorded and used for the planning of future activities and reporting.
- Regular communication with participants was maintained through a mailbox to keep members engaged and informed about ongoing and future activities.

The outcomes were that the objectives are well-defined as well as activities, and follow-up plans for the CoPs. There was an active participation from all members, ensuring the CoP is driven by shared goals and contributions.

Identification & Engagement of CoP Members:

As indicated in D2.1, the identification of CoP members goes beyond the EIC beneficiaries and include key stakeholders as crucial elements for the CoP management and animation. After the initial elaboration of stakeholders' list, the methodology for the engagement of motivated and active stakeholders has followed the described steps: methodology:

- Taking into account the initial stakeholders identification that occurred during the proposal writing phase
- Mobilisation of project partners and project stakeholders: EIC PMs as well as projects partners communicate a list of stakeholders for the mapping process, this aims at improving the co-creation process.
- Exploring networks and initiatives of project partners APRE, EurA, and EBN, that have extensive connections with stakeholders.
- Review and validation during the co-creation workshop of the objectives of the project and this is supplemented with inputs from EIC PMs, they indicate the deep-tech projects they want to qualify for each CoP.
- Development of a comprehensive co-creation process (workshops, surveys, desk research, etc.) and the organisation of the co-creation workshops that were instead called the 'community building workshops'
- Identification of CoP members extended through the organization of 'open calls' relayed and promoted through the project communication channels.
- Organisation of open info sessions to promote the EIC project (CSA) and advertise the benefits of taking part in it

Once the stakeholders are identified, strategic engagement enhances outcomes and ensures alignment with CoP objectives. The tailored engagement strategies for stakeholders are developed by project partners. For instance, D2.4 presented a general strategy for stakeholders, outlining that each CoP would have its own flow and management with the assigned EBN manager and thematic expert. They are intended to meet with EIC PMs to consult jointly on activities to be planned. This could entail utilizing diverse communication channels, organizing events, forums, or platforms catering to each group's preferences.

Categories within CoP Members:

CoP Members, as defined in D2.1 are categorised, and they include:

- EIC Project Participants: Directly engaged individuals in EIC-funded projects selected by the PMs, such as researchers, innovators, entrepreneurs, scientists, engineers, etc.
- EIC Project Stakeholders: Beyond participants, those with interests in EIC project, including policymakers, government representatives, industry leaders, investors, etc. they include more precisely:
 - Industry and Corporate Representatives: Companies interested in partnering or collaborating with EIC projects, including established corporations, startups, or industries seeking innovation opportunities.
 - Investors and Funders: Entities offering financial support or investment opportunities for EIC projects, like venture capitalists or funding institutions.

- **Research Institutions and Academia:** Involved in collaborative research, knowledge exchange, or providing expertise to EIC projects.
- **Government and Regulatory Bodies:** Overseeing or regulating aspects related to the projects, including compliance, standards, or policymaking.
- **Entrepreneurial Ecosystem:** Providing resources, mentorship, or guidance to startups involved in EIC projects, such as incubators, accelerators, or innovation hubs.

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Key Attributes of CoP Management:

Ownership & Commitment

Ownership and commitment are important attributes in the effective management of a CoP. Ownership comes with a sense of responsibility and accountability among members. When individuals within the CoP take ownership of their roles and contributions, they actively engage, share knowledge, and drive initiatives forward. Also, commitment, should be ensured with sustained participation. This establishes the groundwork for continuity, enabling the CoP to evolve and remain relevant over time.

The use of dedicated e-mail addresses for the communication with each group of CoP members reinforce from one side the ownership and commitment:

- CoP Industry - industry@eicommunities.eu
- CoP CleanTech - cleantech@eicommunities.eu
- CoP Health - health@eicommunities.eu

Building Relationships:

A fundamental aspect of CoPs is nurturing relationships among members. This involves encouraging dialogue, active listening, and inclusive decision-making.

Having a collaborative approach that ensures members feel valued and part of the CoP's journey, using co-creation, mutual learning, and shared goals.

During the community building workshops held in February and March 2024, this aspect was evident and even more during the organization of thematic webinars and pitching session of June 2024. EIC beneficiaries long to share information, initiatives and opportunities. The creation of LinkedIn Groups for each CoP aims to answer to the need and give the possibility to the EIC beneficiaries to freely dialogue among then in a user-friendly mode and in a effective way:

- [Industry Community of Practice](#)
- [Health Community of Practice](#)
- [Cleantech Community of Practice](#)

Feedback, Adaptation, and Fine-tuning:

Continuous feedback, adaptation, and fine-tuning within the described framework are crucial elements in CoP development. Regular evaluation, post-meetings or post-events, periodic surveys, and specific thematic co-creation sessions engage CoP members effectively. In order to guarantee the success of feedback activities, partners have adopted the use of online tools as Mentimeter¹ that allow CoP Members to provide their feedback and comment during the meetings and events. This is the most effective way essentially for three reasons: 1) to guarantee the engagement of CoP members 2) to provide an immediate first answer to their comments and remarks that increase their feeling of commitment 3) to ensure an exchange of opinions in real time between the EIC Communities project team and the meeting participants.

Understanding the changing nature of stakeholder's involvement is important as their roles might change due to various factors such as organizational changes or loss of interests and

¹ <https://www.mentimeter.com>

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loss of value perceived from participating in the CoP. Therefore, adaptation to the CoPs needs is key to maintaining an inclusive and responsive CoP, but always following the scope described in this document.

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CoP Engagement & Facilitation

CoP engagement and facilitation are vital for fostering collaboration and innovation within the EIC deep-tech ecosystem. By uniting diverse stakeholders—researchers, industry experts, project managers, and policymakers—CoPs create dynamic platforms for knowledge exchange and synergies. This section provides key strategies for building and sustaining vibrant CoPs, enhancing the impact of EIC-funded projects as well as lessons learned and recommendations from the first phases of the project.

CoP Members Engagement

In recruiting members for a CoP an approach focused on creating a diverse and inclusive community is considered:

- **Consider diversity:** To identify potential members, it's important to emphasize diversity in roles, experience levels, and perspectives. In practice, each CoP begins by defining the member profiles and the desired number of individuals in each category to ensure a well-balanced group.
- **Articulate the value proposition of the CoP:** in other terms 'what's in it for them?', what are the benefits in participating at an individual level but also at an organisational/institutional one. This is essential to secure future commitment and ownership from the members.
- **Target the outreach:** Project partners along with EIC PMs engage in targeted outreach through various channels, including industry forums, professional networks, social media platforms, and specialized publications within the CoP's domain. Customized messaging tailored to specific profiles encourages their active participation.
- **Leverage existing connections:** Project partners along with EIC PMs leverage existing partnerships with relevant organizations in identifying potential members. Additionally, a referral process involves collaborating entities recommending or nominating suitable candidates for CoP membership has proven highly valuable in previous initiatives.
- **Networking:** Participation in industry events, workshops, and conferences as well as online platforms events related to CoP topics provides networking opportunities to connect with potential members. Identifying these events through industry-specific online platforms or social media communities helps target professionals interested in CoP activities.
- **Collecting data:** Through surveys, needs assessments, informational sessions, and webinars about CoP goals and membership benefits encourages potential members and their engagement.

In concluding this section, partners should always ensure diversity in outreach efforts by targeting various demographics, sectors, geographic regions, and professional affiliations to build a well-rounded CoP with diverse perspectives. With all the methods mentioned, the CoP aims to attract a diverse range of members, contributing varied roles, experiences, and perspectives, thereby enriching the community, and having a dynamic exchange of knowledge and ideas.

Lessons Learned & Recommendations

Following the implementation of activities in the first phase of the project, the following lessons learned, and recommendations were identified, they aim at engaging EIC deep-tech projects and stakeholders effectively.

- Engagement of stakeholders: Engaging stakeholders such as technical experts, universities, commercial partners, and funders is crucial. Technical experts and universities provide necessary knowledge and skills for project development, while commercial partners and funders are key to market introduction and scaling. They are identified through the partners network and are involved within the CoP activities such as thematic workshops and pitching sessions.
- Implementing diverse exploitation strategies: This includes TRL upscaling, direct commercialization, and licensing. Emphasizing commercialization over research can lead to better market readiness and impact and this was highlighted through the co-creation workshops where attendees emphasized the need for identify potential clients to test their projects.
- Facilitating funding: Projects with higher TRLs require significant financial investments for further research and development. Ensuring sufficient funding is vital for advancing these projects to a market-ready stage. In further phases of the project, potential investors will be included in activities and events, while EIC projects are getting ready with pitching through current activities.
- The recommendations would be to organize and promote workshops and events focused on community building and always encouraging project managers and stakeholders to actively participate, share insights, and collaborate on common challenges.
- As it can be seen from previous deliverables and namely deliverable 1.5, it is key to develop targeted strategies to engage stakeholders. Regular communication, updates, and involvement in project milestones can foster stronger relationships and commitment as well as using personalized interactions to address specific stakeholder needs and interests.
- It is also essential to provide dedicated support and resources for EIC PMs to engage with stakeholders and EIC projects effectively. This could include training on stakeholder management, tools for tracking engagement activities, and platforms for collaborative communication.
- It is always better to prefer real-world applications of project outcomes by highlighting case studies, success stories, and tangible benefits to demonstrate the impact and potential of the projects. This is typically done through the platform and through social media by showcasing EIC projects success stories.
- Facilitating Knowledge Sharing by creating mechanisms for knowledge sharing among projects, such as the use of the LinkedIn online platforms that aims at encouraging members to share lessons learned, best practices, and innovative solutions.

CoP Leadership & Facilitation

An essential component in managing successfully a CoP is the leadership and facilitation skills. To ensure effective guidance, EBN has selected EBN team members and appointed managers for each CoPs. They will be supported by a 'technical expert' from the EBN Special Interest Groups (<https://ebn.eu/special-interest-groups/>). The facilitator/CoP managers, selected based on their prior experience in managing Special Interest Groups (SIGs), bring a wealth of expertise in fostering collaboration, facilitating discussions, and driving initiatives that align with the CoP's objectives.

The appointed facilitators have previous experience in managing the SIGs. They have project management experience in sectors such as circular economy, space, industry, sustainability, social entrepreneurship, etc. They act as the main focal point and work together with the SIG chair, considered as the 'technical expert'.

Three thematic experts have been selected through a call for applications that was released first internally, targeting EBN SIG members, then general EBN members not belonging to a SIG and finally, in the last weeks of the call, advertised to the general public. Applications received were selected by an internal committee composed of EBN SIG Managers. Three thematic experts were selected respectively for the Health, CleanTech and Industry CoPs. They underwent a preliminary meeting to assess further their applications. The next steps include meeting with project partners, with EIC PMs and the preparation of future activities planned for quarter four of 2024. For this, regular meetings will be scheduled to organize such activities with EBN SIG managers.

Experts were selected on the basis of their CV, belonging to a recognised organisation, their expertise in the sector in focus and motivation to take part in the project.

*

The CoP Manager and Technical Expert hold **essential responsibilities**:

- Guiding the CoP members in meeting the set objectives as per the co-creation workshops
- Ensuring that the CoP remains aligned with its purpose and objectives.
- Overseeing the relevance of planned activities
- Facilitating and moderating sessions/meetings
- Fostering an environment of collaboration and knowledge exchange
- Overseeing the development of a complete calendar of activities and community building activities
- Ensuring the proper communication with the CoP and beyond (across CoPs)
- Ensuring the proper collection of feedback and evaluation mechanisms from the CoP stakeholders
- Making sure members remain engaged and keep on participating in activities. Enquiring for lack of involvement from members.
- Addressing any issues or challenges that may arise within the CoP.
- Communicate and refer monthly to the CSA project coordinator (APRE)

Regarding **the CoP manager/ facilitator soft skills**, they must/should:

- Demonstrate effective communication skills and active listening.
- Have strong moderation skills, ensuring inclusive engagement among all CoP members.

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- Adapt to changing needs given the evolving nature of the CoP, while adjusting the objectives if needed, aligning with membership dynamics, and with industry trends.

In conclusion, effective leadership and facilitation are not just about steering the CoP, but about cultivating an environment that thrives on collaboration, learning, and adaptation. In the coming weeks, the actual mobilisation of technical experts will happen and the preparation for Q4 activities will resume.

Activities within the CoPs

Workshops & Meetings

The CoP manager, in collaboration with various stakeholders, should carefully consider the design and implementation of CoP activities, taking into consideration several factors such as member's needs and interests, providing value, engagement strategies, evaluation mechanisms, and inclusivity. Activities will revolve around some main formats:

- **Needs Assessment:** an essential first component needed to identify gaps and requirements within a specific context. It ensures that the project partners are aligned with the initial needs of the project. A needs assessment was conducted in the first months and was intended at supporting the selection of EIC projects and devising a strategy to engage EIC PMs in the CSA project. The CSA team actively encouraged the direct participation of EIC PMs and other representatives in a dedicated co-creation workshop held in Brussels on October 23, 2023, as outlined in the DoA. During this workshop, EIC PMs were invited to discuss the status, strengths, challenges, and obstacles encountered in supporting the existing set of selected projects. They also shared their vision for developing CoPs within the CSA project. The co-creation process included further desk research; feedback forms, surveys, interviews with key stakeholders. The findings of this needs assessment are found in D1.1. In conclusion, the insights gathered from the EIC PMs are crucial in refining the selection and organization of EIC thematic and challenge-driven portfolios and associated projects earmarked for CoPs.
- **Co-creation Workshops & Kick-off Meeting:** the CSA team have initiated the CoP journey with 3 co-creation workshops. They served as a starting point to introduce CoP members, outlining expectations, goals, and guidelines. The co-creation workshop encourages active participation from members, encouraging collaboration in defining the CoP's objectives, structure, and activities. It helped to set the tone for the CoP's purpose, promoting a shared understanding and commitment among members. More specifically, the online co-creation workshops (3) were organised in February and March 2024. They gathered beneficiaries of all projects grouped in the respective CoPs, relevant EIC PMs and other CoP stakeholders (including investors, market experts, research and academia, entrepreneurial ecosystems, etc). Three co-creation workshops were organised as per the following:
 - a plenary session where the Project team presented the project, the CoP structures, and planned activities,
 - break-out sessions for each set of selected projects included in the CoP– to identify the specific needs and expectations towards the project and to tailor accordingly community and synergy building activities for each CoP.
- **Thematic Webinars:** facilitating learning opportunities is key within a CoP. Members benefit from accessing resources that enhance their knowledge relevant to the CoP's domain. To achieve this, the CoP can organize and connect members with relevant thematic webinars, workshops, or industry-specific courses.
- **Skill Development Trainings:** Additionally, organizing skill-focused sessions within the CoP or inviting experts for specialized webinar further enriches members' skill

sets. Collaborations with educational institutions or industry partners part of EBN network can provide access to specialized courses.

Typical activities to be conducted within CoPs

1. **Online pitching sessions (2):** where EIC project representatives have the opportunity to pitch their project activities and results. The aim is to promote sharing of best practices as well as access to potential investment opportunities, links to corporate or industries and will indirectly benefit the projects. EIC project will receive exposure through the communication channels. Within M10 (June 2024) the first round of pitching sessions were organized:
 - 21st of June: CoP Health
 - 26th of June: CoP Industry
 - 28th of June: CoP CleanTech

And the events are posted and updated with list of interested projects on the DEEPSYNC platform: <https://deepsync.eu/event/discover-innovations-at-the-heart-of-european-innovation-council-eic-upcoming-pitching-sessions/>

Pitching sessions receives a wide visibility through the communication channels as they are open to the EIC beneficiaries that can pitch their projects but also to the wide range of potential stakeholders. It is important in this context to clarify that the scope of these initiatives is not the same of the pitching sessions with investors and venture capitalists: even if they could be stakeholders, they are not the primary target. Pitching sessions want to attract research centers, universities, corporates, business development organizations etc. That can be partners for future projects, technology transfer or that can support the access to market. After each pitching session a follow up is made to share among participants relevant materials of the EIC projects and to collect requests of bilateral meetings to explore the cooperation opportunities.

2. **Online thematic webinars/workshops (2):** this is part of building the capacities of projects. The specific topics were identified in the co-creation sessions as they need to answer the specific needs. They are delivered by experts in the identified field. They can be related to business skills (building financial capacities, access to funding, etc.) or soft skills (presentation, pitching, etc.) or more scientific/ technical subjects that are particular to those CoP members' needs. Within M10 (June 2024) two thematic webinars were organized and one will be organized at the beginning of July. The webinar topics are found out from the inputs provided by the CoP members, according to this the community building workshops held in February and March were fundamental to detect the topics of interest:
 - "IP strategy & management" (webinar held on 7th June 2024),
 - "scaling & go to market strategies" (webinar held on 14th June 2024),
 - "investor approach" (to be implemented on 8th July 2024).

As the topics identified by the CoP members are horizontal, the EIC Communities project partners decided to let them open to all the three CoPs participate. The last part of each thematic webinar agenda is dedicated to a satisfaction survey that is launched live and that allows not only to collect feedback on organizational aspects

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but also on further topics to be developed during the EIC Communities project activities.

3. **Portfolio days** (2): (online) organised in each CoP, moderated by CoP managers with the support of technical experts, they will gather projects' beneficiaries (from EIC thematic and challenge-driven projects), PMs and EIC representatives as well as relevant CoP stakeholders. The detailed content will be subject to determination within the co-creation process; however, they should include:
 - Panel discussions on latest policy/regulatory insights and technological breakthroughs related to the CoP focus.
 - Latest achievements of each CoP set of selected projects.
 - Presentations of selected projects (objectives, latest results, research/exploitation needs, etc).
4. **Information Days**: the CSA team will collaborate with the EIC to support the organization of the Information Days and involve the CoP members.

Content and Knowledge Sharing within the CoP

Within the CoP, sharing knowledge and insights is what keeps the momentum and the collaboration running. This section explores how exchange of information happens within the CoP, best practices, and the sharing success stories among members. This was further assessed with the co-creation workshops where the tools and methods were used to communicate effectively, encourage active participation, curate valuable resources, and celebrate achievements. The following main points were considered:

- **Selecting the right communication and collaboration platforms**: this is crucial for CoP members as there are various tools, from emails to comprehensive online platforms that offer different functionalities. Careful consideration should prioritize accessibility and acceptance among CoP members, as resistance to adopting essential platforms may hinder efficient sharing of insights and resources. During co-creation workshops, dedicated channels were identified and defined for each activity, utilizing diverse formats to accommodate different preferences. Projects partners eventually decided to create a LinkedIn group for each CoP where news and opportunities would be posted. This will also serve as a **Knowledge Management System** where relevant stories resources, and case studies are curated in a user-friendly repository (the DeepSynC platform) categorized by themes, topics, or expertise areas. Regular updates maintain its relevance, encouraging continuous learning. Finally, the CoP serves as a platform to **recognize and showcase achievements and success stories** as emphasized by PMs. This is done through the DeepSynC platform, to celebrate accomplishments, acknowledge contributions, and inspire others within the CoP. Sharing success stories not only motivates and educates members but also transforms the DeepSynC platform into a vibrant hub for knowledge exchange, collaboration, and inspiration within the CoP.

Sustainability of the CoP:

Sustainability within a CoP is essential for its longevity and continued effectiveness beyond the project duration. Some tangible ways to address and ensure the sustainability of a CoP, are listed below:

- **Seeking feedback periodically:** CSA team has put in place mechanisms to collect inputs such as implementing a feedback mechanism to gather member's input on CoP activities. . As mentioned earlier, and following every community building session, thematic session or pitching session, project partners have collected feedback through online questionnaires. First, these were administered after the sessions. However, and as an improvement, real-time feedback was collected in the last session, anonymously, allowing for more responses and the possibility to answer any negative comments on the spot.
- **Establishing a feedback loop for continuous improvement:** using automated surveys sent via emails after meetings or events to gather specific feedback and further analyse this feedback and incorporate suggestions for future activities. The members are able rate the session content, delivery, and dynamics, provide comments, and suggest topics for future discussions. Based on the feedback it is essential to adapt the structure and activities accordingly.
- **Providing a continuous evaluation of the CoP performance:** by regularly assessing the CoP's effectiveness against predefined objectives, such as:
 - Members attendance: registration and attendance to the sessions
 - Members engagement: tracking the number of active participants in discussions.
 - Usage of the platforms: usage and contributions, monitoring the frequency of visits, downloads, or interactions with shared articles, resources, and case studies, etc.
- **Collaboration:** tracking the number of joint projects, cross-functional collaborations, or co-created resources, as well as instances of mentorship, networking, or peer-to-peer support within the CoP. The introduction of the LinkedIn groups will facilitate the collaboration aspect.
- **Planning for sustainability and scalability from the outset:** Project partners will integrate from the co-creation process, considerations on how to design the CoP with the sustainability aspect in mind; this will feed D3.3 Sustainability strategy (including Dissemination and Communication) It should consider how the CoP will grow and evolve beyond the project duration.
 - In case EIC Programme Managers foresee to have a sustainability plan for the CoPs, the plan could include strategies for accommodating a larger community, integrating new members, and diversifying activities as the CoP expands. At the same time, and of utmost importance identifying successors for key roles within the CoP to ensure continuity. This involves preparing individuals or nominating new ones who can step into important roles as the community grows. An example would be to designate experienced CoP members as mentors to newer members, gradually involving them in leadership roles and responsibilities until they are ready to exchange roles.

Conclusion

The EIC Communities Project aims to foster collaboration and innovation within the European Innovation Council's funded projects. By creating thematic CoPs in CleanTech, Industry, and Health sectors, this project aims to cultivate inclusive environments that facilitate multidisciplinary interactions, knowledge exchange, and innovative ideas.

Throughout this report, the framework for governing and managing these CoPs has been outlined, emphasizing the critical role of stakeholder engagement, defined objectives, and ongoing adaptability within the defined scope. The CoP's purpose, methodology, activities, and sustainability measures have been comprehensively detailed, highlighting the dedication to creating vibrant, long-lasting communities centred on innovation and cross-sector collaboration.

Moreover, the report emphasizes the importance of diverse and inclusive membership, active engagement strategies, and the leadership's commitment to nurturing an environment conducive to learning, feedback, and continuous improvement. It underlines the need for agility in response to evolving project dynamics, stakeholder roles, and industry trends, all while staying aligned with the CoP's defined scope.

The future path of these CoPs stands on the pillars of ongoing evaluation, active member participation, robust communication, and a keen eye on scalability and sustainability beyond the project's duration. As these communities evolve and expand, their success centres on adaptability, member-driven contributions, and the anticipation to prepare future members to ensure continuity and growth.

This report serves as a foundational roadmap for the effective governance, management, and sustainable growth of the EIC Communities of Practice.